

**AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE
TRAINING ACTIVITIES OF FIRMS**

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Abstract: The purpose of the current study was to search for a link between the characteristics of firms' training activities and the characteristics of the organizations themselves. The validity of our hypothesis was examined on the basis of structured interviews. On the basis of the data we can state that the growth in the increase in the number of employees and the innovative nature of technology used have been accompanied by a parallel growth in the training behavior of firms. In our study we attempted to study in detail the influence that the stage the firm is at on its life cycle curve has on the training provided to employees.

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Introductory considerations

Theoretical overview

Today the necessity and importance of educational activities within organizations is unarguable. Nowadays one of the most important resources for a firm is people, their skills and abilities, their knowledge and, in a given situation, their specialist expertise.

It may well be that the crisis unfolding in the economic sphere has reduced the willingness of firms to train workers, but it is also worth considering whether it is precisely those firms that have not neglected staff training that will find it easier to emerge from the less favorable climate caused by the crisis.

Workplace training is not only different from other forms of training in that employees are involved, but also in that generally it is financed by the employer, although this is not exclusively so (since part of the cost can also be borne by the employee). The research field of firm training is a very important research area, because, as we shall see later, up to the time our research was conducted Hungarian companies had not - according to our findings - devoted sufficient time, energy and last, but not least, money to the development of their employees' skills and competences.

One theoretical starting point for our research was Gery Becker's book, *Human Capital, A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to*

Education, which appeared in 1964, and gave a theory of human capital which was the first widely recognized model which also dealt with the theoretical aspects of firm training. His theory distinguished between two types: general and specialist training. General training improves the employee's productivity at any firm, while specialist training enables workers to acquire firm-specific knowledge. While "...in the former case the employee receives an appropriate wage for the marginal productivity, and the training costs are entirely borne by him/her, in the case of special training the wage received is lower than the marginal productivity, and the training costs and the rewards of training are shared between the two parties" (Becker, 1964, p.11-29). At the same time, Becker himself accepted that "... these two pure forms of training are very rare; workplace training includes elements of both the general and specialized theory" (Becker, 1964, p.18). Concerning the interaction between general and specialized training, the article by Kessler and Lülffessman (2002) also points out that, according to the authors, there is a complementary, supplementary relationship between general and specialized training in the sense that the employer, through the financing of specialized training has the opportunity to invest in the general human capital of the employee, and vice versa (Kessler and Lülffessman, 2002, p.2).

The literature dealing with the management of human resources approaches firm training from a different perspective. In this approach training is important for the firm from another perspective, i.e. that it serves to help with settling in to the job, with fulfilling work-related tasks appropriately and with motivation and career development. In relation to the literature on management, we have built on work linked to Armstrong (1999) and Fisher, Schoenfeldt and Shaw (1999). We must, however, be aware that the educational activities described in the literature in many cases were far removed from practice, as has been empirically demonstrated both internationally and in Hungary. We will introduce these surveys in the following section.

Empirical research into firm training

Training financed by the firm has been the subject of wide-ranging international empirical research. The following review features research studies, focusing on the factors studied which were used to analyze the characteristics of workplace training; we will also consider on the basis of which characteristics the training was studied:

- the size of the organization, the strength of the trade unions and the level of their organization, the nature of the workforce, the level of development of the domestic labor market, the complexity of the environment (Knoke and Kalleberg, 1994)
- the size of the organization, the strength of the trade unions and the level of their organization, the expected length of time of a worker's employment, the location of the branch of industry within the economy, who initiated participation in the training, evaluation of the effectiveness of the training (Frazis, Herz and Horrigan, 1995)

- the size of the organization, the strength of the trade unions and the level of their organization, the expected length of time of a worker's employment, the location of the branch of industry within the economy, who initiated participation in the training, the level of fluctuation, the formality of the training, the number of hours devoted to training, the measurement of the effectiveness of the training (Frazis, Gittleman, Horrigan and Joyce, 1998)
- the level of expenditure devoted to training, the number of days devoted to training, the measurement of the demand for training, the method used to initiate training, evaluation of the effectiveness of training, the form of training used, the content of the training (Hegewish and Brewster, 1993)
- the frequency of training, the cost-benefit analysis of the training, the effect of trade unions and the competitiveness of the product market (Bassini, Booth, Brunello, Paola and Leuven, 2005).

One of the largest European data collection projects is the Continuing Vocational Training Survey (hereinafter CVTS), which is organized by Eurostat every five years. This data collection allows an international comparison, and shows detailed statistics about the amount of training, its content, investment made in training and, for example, the areas of training strategy and management (CEDEFOP, 2010, p.10).

During the CVTS research firms with more than 10 employees are contacted, and are then divided according to data collection criteria; here we will only list the most significant groups questioned:

- willingness to support training (a special chapter is devoted to the analysis of those firms who do not support training)
- in the case of firms offering continuous specialist training, attention is paid to the following data: number of participants, time devoted to training, costs of training, evaluation of training
- in the case of firms supporting other types of training, only the participation is measured (CEDEFOP, 2010, p.105-112).

Hungary also participated in the two latest CVTS research cycles, and from the survey carried out in 2005, 4510 statistically assessable questionnaires were returned (CEDEFOP, 2010, p.120).

From international empirical research it is observable that a wide range of criteria were considered, with which researchers attempted to explain and throw light on the motivation behind training financed by employers. The most frequently examined criteria were the number of employees, the industrial sector and the technology used. In this study we would like to consider whether there is a connection between the life cycle of organizations and training.

Our research background

One of the research studies which I took part in was linked to the OTKA grant No. T034249, entitled "The system of interests in adult education". This research was carried out between 2002 and 2003, and the objective was to

analyze the motivation and interest of various actors (individuals, employers, the state) in adult education. Beyond an introduction to theoretical approaches, we conducted empirical data collection, partly through questionnaires and partly through structured interviews. The basic hypothesis of the research was that firms of differing sizes and ownership structures had differing educational practices, and in essence the hypothesis was confirmed (Barizsné Hadházi and Polónyi, (eds.), 2004).

Following an understanding of the literature discussed above and the establishment of the empirical analyses, we attempted to find further bases on which to be able to describe and characterize an organization's educational activities more accurately.

These new analytical criteria included the nature of the technology used by the firm and the position occupied by the firm in the life cycle curve. We only found one example of an analysis of this latter aspect in the specialist literature, namely, Miller's 1985 study "Educational focus in the life cycle of organizations" (Miller, 1985, p.23-26).

In our present study we have re-analyzed the data from the previous research, and although 10 years have since passed, we can, given the economic crisis that has occurred since then, presume that in the educational behavior of firms it is stagnation and retrenchment, much more than progress and development, which can be observed. Even if in many cases it is clear that it is precisely those firms which have not neglected their workers' specialized education that have been able to escape more easily and rapidly from the crisis.

Research introducing the educational behavior of firms

Research questions and methodology

On the basis of an analysis of the theoretical and empirical literature, as well as our own previous research results, our research question was the following: "How are the main features of firms' educational behavior influenced by firm size, the ownership structure, the technology employed and the firm's position on the life cycle curve?"

On the basis of the criteria defined we analyzed the characteristics of firms' training policy through the following dimensions:

- the size of the firm (micro-, small-, medium- or large firms),
- the technology used by the firm (technological pioneer, user of leading technology, firm adopting technology or firm using traditional technology),
- the organization's position on the life cycle curve (newly-formed firm, firm in the growth stage, firm in the mature/stable phase, firm in the declining stage).

We must, however, note that the above dimensions probably influence the firms' training policy to differing degrees. On the basis of empirical research carried out thus far, it seems that it is rather the size of the firm, the ownership

structure and the technology employed that plays the main role, while the industrial sector and the firm's position in the life cycle curve has a secondary importance.

We examined the educational activities from the following perspectives:

- the extent of planning in the training policy: by this we meant whether the firm's training activity was an ad hoc, or a partly, or entirely consciously planned process
- the organized nature of the training policy: in this regard we examined what organizational framework was used to help conduct the training, i.e. if there was an individual, or perhaps a whole team, who was assigned to this HR resource development function, or perhaps the training was carried out by the whole organizational unit
- the HR development objective: the question focused on what objectives the companies' training achieved; these could be motivational, retention or career development goals
- the financial aspects of the training activities: here we analyzed the amount of money spent on training, and also as a proportion of annual income and annual remuneration for individuals
- whether there existed an operative system for measuring the effectiveness of training: i.e. was there monitoring after the training had been held, to reveal how satisfied the participants were, or whether the training had ended with clear results, and whether there had been, or was, a positive result for the firm
- the predominant form of training: the question here was which of the following forms of training dominated in a given type of organization: school attendance-type training, non-school attendance-type training, training within the firm, other types.

In methodological terms the research was basically qualitative, by which we mean that the observable facts were in large measure not expressible numerically and the research did not require that all facts be expressed in this way. Our research was also inductive in that we attempted to formulate conclusions from individual cases, and then generalize them. We used the questionnaire and case studies from the previously mentioned OTKA research. The questionnaire analysis was based on the data from 52 firms, and a further 8 structured interviews, which then led to case studies. The case studies made possible an organized collection of information and deeper analysis than the questionnaire research on its own, and gave a fuller picture of the characteristics observed, as well as anticipating what might be worth analyzing in the future. We must further emphasize that the research was based on a secondary examination of data: the accuracy of the hypothesis was demonstrated by the so-called critical source analysis method, i.e. we re-examined the earlier data and case descriptions through the dimensions described above.

Research results

The firm size dimension

In examining the size of the firm the key factor was the number of employees. According to the most frequently used categories, a micro firm has less than 10 employees, a small firm between 10 and 49, a medium-sized firm between 50 and 250, and a large firm more than 250.

In the analysis according to firm size the case studies were only partially able to confirm our hypothesis.

Our first hypothesis was: the size of the firm has a fundamental influence on the firm's training behavior. Our research proved that, with the exception of large firms, an increase in firm size was accompanied by more developed training activities (more conscious, more planned, more organized and comprehensive). In the case of large firms, however, the situation was more complicated; here, in addition to the number of employees the industrial sector and the ownership structure also had an effect on the firm's training behavior.

In relation to the training-related activities of the smaller size firms it can be stated that in order for their employees to be able to carry out their tasks at work, they were forced to finance training which was often based on legal requirements, and therefore in the majority of cases this was a school type training course, or some kind of taught course (and the firms did not support these courses if it could be avoided, but rather sought to choose courses according to their working task-related aspects). If employees were involved in further courses in addition to this, these were of an ad hoc nature, with financial support only appearing occasionally (the most probable reason for this was that HR management activities were also at a low level in the firm, and employee training fell outside the management's long term planning, in terms of the planning, realization and monitoring of such training).

The training practice of medium-sized firms was more frequent, but was also not characterized by planning, and there was a real attempt to limit expenditure on training, with courses more geared to a motivational function; here too, any monitoring of the effectiveness of training was not typical.

With large firms, the higher number of employees did not by itself bring with it a more developed training behavior; the situation was much more complex, and thus other dimensions must be taken into consideration in addition to the size of the firm (e.g. the technology employed, the ownership structure).

The dimension of the technology used by the firm

In order to examine the technology used by the firm we grouped the firms according to the categories used by EURAB.

In terms of the technology used by the firm, the following four types were established:

- technology pioneers

- users of leading technology
- adopters of technology, and
- users of traditional technology (EURAB, 2004, p.6).

In the case of the technology used by the firm our hypothesis was that the technology employed has a significant influence on the training behavior of the firm.

The following statements can be made:

Technology pioneer firms and users of leading technology had a conscious and planned educational policy, with training characterized by a strategic approach, a carefully thought-out financial attitude and a process of monitoring for effectiveness.

Firms adopting technology built their developmental activities on a smaller budget, with special attention devoted to teaching how to use the adopted technology, but with a low level of training activity related to investment goals.

From the use of technology perspective, those firms using traditional technology had a low level education policy, of an ad hoc nature. Little money was spent on training, which was mainly of a catch-up or compulsory nature.

The dimension of the position occupied by the firm in the life cycle curve

The life cycle model has a history going back about 50 years. The first studies to deal with how the life of a company might be divided up appeared in the 1960s (for example, Lippitt and Schmidt, 1967). As the attention of researchers spread over this new field, more models were created, which naturally showed both similarities and differences, in the sense, for example, of how many phases characterized the life of an organization from its creation to its disappearance, as well as on what basis the different phases of the life cycle could be separated.

The simplest models created just three phases, as in, for example, Lippitt at Schmidt (1967), while the volume published (also in Hungarian) by Ichak Adizes in 1992 identified 10 periods.

When studying the life cycle phases of the firm, researchers generally followed the changes in the firm structure, and its different features, its centralization and its formalization, but they also devoted attention to the development of the firm's culture, its financial situation, the technology used to produce the goods or provide the services offered, the firm's current market position and changes to this, and the firm's innovativeness.

During our analysis we divided the firm life cycle curve into four phases: the beginning or foundation of the life cycle, growth, maturity and stability, and decline. According to our hypothesis the position the firm occupies in the life cycle significantly influences its training behavior. We were not able to analyze firms in the initial and decline phases due to the limited number of case studies available to us, but it can be rationally accepted that in these two phases the management and owners were not focused on providing further training for employees. The results from the growth and stability periods supported the

idea that towards the peak of the life cycle it was increasingly the conscious, planned and comprehensive training behavior that characterized the firm.

Our findings were the following:

During the growth phase the HR department came into being, and carried out a more or less conscious educational policy. It was during this phase that the processes and methods which the organization would later use to train its employees started to form. The firm researched the training market and tried to meet its demands with the most appropriate educational methods. The circle of those involved in educational activities became wider and wider. However, the opportunities for participation were already restricted (i.e. it was mainly management levels that were involved) as were the funds available. The demand for education was perhaps most important during this phase, since it was, in a certain sense, also the source of growth and development.

The most intensive educational policy was experienced in the maturity and stability phase, and mainly in the latter, since here the resources, the structure, and external and internal effectiveness work towards a situation in which the employees were treated as a significantly important resource; and firms saw that the key to long term success lay in the human factor. Almost all types of firm training made their appearance, the educational policy became organized and conscious and the funds devoted to these activities were most significant in this phase. Participants in training included all hierarchical levels of the firm and this phase also saw the appearance of an efficiency assessment of training.

Conclusion

We have considered training initiated by employers from the perspectives of both human capital and the literature related to management, and we have also drawn readers' attention to the fact that in reality the training activities of companies fell somewhere between the two, in the sense that only in a few cases (i.e. when certain firm characteristics and conditions were satisfied) did organizations consider employee training an investment (here there was a difference in the approaches to human capital). At the same time the results of the empirical research did not match the behavior described in the management literature. It could, however, be stated that the use of innovative technology and the progress of a firm on the life cycle curve was accompanied by a more intensive training activity.

It is also worth drawing attention to the fact that regardless of which range of companies we choose to conduct research with, there will always be individual differences, and peculiar features of different firms in which the training behavior in the given firm diverges from the average or general tendencies, as indeed we have seen in examples from our research results.

The present state of research requires further studies, since our individual hypotheses remain limited due to the very restricted samples available to us to confirm the hypotheses. In any case, further examinations are necessary in these firm categories.

It would be advisable to bring the samples forward in time; i.e. to refresh the case studies, since in the almost 10 years that have elapsed, the training

behavior of firms may have changed. We might expect that in this time some forward progress might have occurred in this field, although as a result of the crisis this is difficult to envisage; indeed, in some cases the situation achieved previously has started to deteriorate.

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